

ISic4408

Fragmentary inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

The fragment could not be found by Tréziny in the excavation stores (2011: 129)

Last Change

2019-09-13 - Jonathan Prag created the file based upon Tréziny 2011

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

The fragment was reported in the excavation journal of Fr. Villard for 26 February 1949, recovered in the NE corner of the Hellenistic structure VI,A (=23,24) , west of the agora.

Coordinates

37.204118, 15.181527

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Antiquarium di Megara Hyblaia

Physical Description

Fragment of a marble plaque, of which no detailed description is preserved

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Text is recorded over two lines

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The omicron is described (Tréziny reporting Fr. Villard) as angular

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. ενχρ

2. λιο

Apparatus

Text of Tréziny 2011

Translation (en)**Commentary**

The inscription has not been relocated since the original excavations. Villard only mentions its existence in the publication of 1951 ('un fragment

d'inscription funéraire chrétienne du Ve siècle'); Tréziny reports slightly greater detail from the excavation journal, as recorded here.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Tréziny, Henry 2011. À propos d'une inscription funéraire paléochrétienne de Mégara Hyblaea. *Provence Historique. Hommages à Jean Guyon*. 61: 127-134. At 129

Villard, F 1951. Megara Hyblaea. *Mélanges d'archéologie et d'histoire*. 63: 7-52. At 51 n.2

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